

Studies in the Synthesis of Furochromones. Part I. Synthesis of 5-Oxo-5H-furo (3,2-g) benzopyran Derivatives

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Condensation of 2-methyl resorcinol with ethyl acetoacetate, ethyl- α -methyl-acetoacetate and ethyl benzoylacetate by refluxing it in diphenyl ether gave (Ia), (Ie) and (Ih), which after allylation and Claisen rearrangement gave the *o*-hydroxy allylchromones and flavone, which on cyclisation with con. sulphuric acid followed by dehydrogenation gave (IIIa), (IIIc) and (III d) respectively. The intermediate *o*-hydroxy allyl derivatives were also subjected to ozonolysis followed by cyclisation of the acetaldehyde derivatives to give (IIIb) and (IIIe).

Linear furochromones such as khellin and visnagin possess many physiological properties such as antispasmodic¹⁻³, vasodilating⁴⁻⁶, hypotensive⁷ action etc. In view of this, we report here the syntheses of linear alkyl substituted furochromones and furoflavones.

Condensation of 2-methyl resorcinol with ethyl acetoacetate using diphenyl ether as condensing agent, according to Desai, Trivedi and Sethna⁸, gave 7-hydroxy-2,8-dimethylchromone (Ia), which on allylation with allyl bromide in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate and dry acetone afforded 7-allyloxy-2,8-dimethylchromone (Ib). (Ib) when refluxed with dimethyl aniline underwent Claisen rearrangement to give 7-hydroxy-6-allyl-2,8-dimethylchromone (Ic), which when triturated with con. sulphuric acid, according to Shaikh and Trivedi⁹ gave 2,7,9-trimethyl-5-oxo-5H-2,3-dihydrofuro(3,2-g) benzopyran (IIa). Dehydrogenation of (IIa) by refluxing it with diphenyl ether using palladium charcoal as catalyst afforded 2,7,9-trimethyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran (IIIa).

7-Hydroxy-6-allyl-2,8-dimethylchromone (Ic) when subjected to ozonolysis according to Seshadri *et al.*¹⁰ gave the corresponding 7-hydroxy-6-acetaldehyde-2,8-dimethylchromone (Id), which on cyclisation with *o*-phosphoric acid resulted in the formation of 7,9-dimethyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran (IIIb).

2-Methyl resorcinol on condensation with ethyl- α -methyl acetoacetate by refluxing it in diphenyl ether, afforded 7-hydroxy-2,3,8-trimethylchromone (Ic), which on allylation, Claisen rearrangement, cyclisation and dehydrogenation gave 2,6,7,9-tetramethyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran (IIIc).

Similar condensation of 2-methyl resorcinol with ethyl benzoyl-acetate gave 7-hydroxy-8-methylflavone (Ih), which when subjected to allylation, Claisen rearrangement, cyclisation and dehydrogenation gave 2,9-dimethyl-7-phenyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran (III d).

7-Hydroxy-6-allyl-8-methylflavone (Ij) on ozonolysis gave the acetaldehyde derivative (Ik), which underwent cyclisation, when heated with *o*-phosphoric acid to give (IIIe).

I

II

III

(I)

- (a) $R = \text{CH}_3$; $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$
 (b) $R = \text{CH}_3$; $R_1 = R_3 = \text{H}$; $R_2 = \text{CH}_2\text{CH} = \text{CH}_2$
 (c) $R = \text{CH}_3$; $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}$; $R_3 = \text{CH}_2\text{CH} = \text{CH}_2$
 (d) $R = \text{CH}_3$; $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}$; $R_3 = \text{CH}_2\text{CHO}$
 (e) $R = R_1 = \text{CH}_3$; $R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$
 (f) $R = R_1 = \text{CH}_3$; $R_2 = \text{CH}_2\text{CH} = \text{CH}_2$; $R_3 = \text{H}$
 (g) $R = R_1 = \text{CH}_3$; $R_2 = \text{H}$; $R_3 = \text{CH}_2\text{CH} = \text{CH}_2$
 (h) $R = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$; $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$
 (i) $R = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$; $R_1 = R_3 = \text{H}$; $R_2 = \text{CH}_2\text{CH} = \text{CH}_2$
 (j) $R = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$; $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}$; $R_3 = \text{CH}_2\text{CH} = \text{CH}_2$
 (k) $R = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$; $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}$; $R_3 = \text{CH}_2\text{CHO}$

(II)

- (a) $R = \text{CH}_3$; $R_1 = \text{H}$
 (b) $R = R_1 = \text{CH}_3$
 (c) $R = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$; $R_1 = \text{H}$

(III)

- (a) $R = R_1 = \text{CH}_3$; $R_2 = \text{H}$
 (b) $R = R_2 = \text{H}$; $R_1 = \text{CH}_3$
 (c) $R = R_1 = R_2 = \text{CH}_3$
 (d) $R = \text{CH}_3$; $R_1 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$; $R_2 = \text{H}$
 (e) $R = R_2 = \text{H}$; $R_1 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$

EXPERIMENTAL

7-Hydroxy-2,8-dimethylchromone (Ia): A mixture of 2-methyl resorcinol (5 g.), ethyl acetoacetate (5 ml.) and diphenyl ether (10 ml.) was refluxed for 3 hr. After cooling the separated product was filtered and washed several times with petroleum ether. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 263°. Yield 3 g. (Found: C, 69.14; H, 5.38. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 69.43; H, 5.26%).

7-Allyloxy-2,8-dimethylchromone (Ib): A mixture of 7-hydroxy-2,8-dimethylchromone (2 g.), allyl bromide (1.8 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (8 g.) was refluxed in dry boiling acetone (150 ml.) on a water bath for 6 hr. The acetone was evaporated and the residue was treated with water. The separated product was filtered, washed with very dilute sodium hydroxide solution and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 105°. Yield 1.3 g. (Found: C, 73.33; H, 6.15. $C_{14}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 73.05; H, 6.05%).

7-Hydroxy-6-allyl-2,8-dimethylchromone (Ic): 7-Allyloxy-2,8-dimethylchromone (2 g.) was refluxed with dimethyl aniline (10 ml.) for 6 hr. After cooling, the reaction mixture was poured into con. hydrochloric acid (30 ml.) containing pieces of ice. The separated product was filtered and dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution. The solution was filtered and the filtrate on acidification with con. hydrochloric acid gave the pure product. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 197°. Yield 1.2 g. (Found: C, 73.23; H, 6.06. $C_{14}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 73.05; H, 6.08%).

2,7,9-Trimethyl-5-oxo-5H-2,3-dihydrofuro(3,2-g)benzopyran (IIa): 7-Hydroxy-6-allyl-2,8-dimethylchromone (1 g.) was triturated with con. sulphuric acid (5 ml.) for 15 mins. on a water bath. The reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice. The separated product was filtered and washed with very dilute sodium hydroxide solution to remove uncyclised compound. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 180°. Yield 0.7 g. (Found: C, 72.81; H, 6.05. $C_{14}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 73.05; H, 6.08%).

2,7,9-Trimethyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran (IIIa): A mixture of 2,7,9-trimethyl-5-oxo-5H-2,3-dihydrofuro(3,2-g)benzopyran (0.5 g.), palladised charcoal (10%; 0.3 g.) and diphenyl ether (3 ml.) was refluxed for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered hot. After cooling, petroleum ether was added to the filtrate. The separated product was filtered, washed several times with petroleum ether and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 223°. Yield 0.25 g. (Found: C, 73.77; H, 5.01. $C_{14}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 73.79; H, 5.26%).

7-Hydroxy-6-acetaldehydro-2,8-dimethylchromone (Id): 7-Hydroxy-6-allyl-2,8-dimethylchromone (1 g.) was dissolved in ethyl acetate (150 ml.) and the solution was cooled to 0–5° by keeping it in freezing mixture. Ozonized oxygen was passed through it for 20 mins. It was subjected to hydrogenation in the presence of palladised charcoal (5%; 0.4 g.) for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered. The solvent was evaporated and the residue was dissolved in benzene. The solution was run over a short column of alumina and the product was eluted with benzene. Benzene was evaporated and the residue crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 219°. Yield 0.6 g. (Found: C, 67.02; H, 5.00. $C_{13}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 67.23; H, 5.05%).

7,9-Dimethyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran (IIIb): 7-Hydroxy-6-acetaldehyde-2,8-dimethylchromone (0.5 g.) was heated with *o*-phosphoric acid (10 ml.) for 1 hr. on a water bath. After cooling, the reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice. The separated product was filtered, washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution and it crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 236°. Yield 0.25 g. (Found: C, 72.93; H, 4.80. $C_{13}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 72.89; H, 4.67%).

7-Hydroxy-2,3,8-trimethylchromone (Ie): A mixture of 2-methyl resorcinol (5 g.), ethyl- α -methyl-acetoacetate (5 ml.) and diphenyl ether (10 ml.) was refluxed for 5 hr. with a short condenser to facilitate the removal of alcohol. The reaction mixture was cooled and the separated compound was filtered and washed several times with petroleum ether. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 274°. Yield 1 g. (Found: C, 70.62; H, 5.60. $C_{12}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 70.69; H, 5.83%).

7-Allyloxy-2,3,8-trimethylchromone (If): A mixture of 7-hydroxy-2,3,8-trimethylchromone (2 g.), allyl bromide (1.8 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (7 g.) was refluxed in dry boiling acetone (200 ml.) for 6 hr. on a water bath. Working up as described earlier the product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 133°. Yield 1.5 g. (Found: C, 73.58; H, 6.37. $C_{15}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 73.77; H, 6.56%).

7-Hydroxy-6-allyl-2,3,8-trimethylchromone (Ig): 7-Allyloxy-2,3,8-trimethylchromone (2 g.) was heated with dimethyl aniline (10 ml.) for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was added into con. hydrochloric acid containing pieces of ice. The compound was ether extracted and the ethereal layer was treated with sodium hydroxide solution. The alkaline layer on acidification gave the 6-allyl derivative while little amount of 7-allyloxy derivative was recovered when the ether was evaporated. 7-Hydroxy-6-allyl-2,3,8-trimethylchromone was filtered, washed with water and dried. The compound was dissolved in benzene and the solution was run over a short column of alumina. The compound was eluted with benzene. After the removal of solvent the residue crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 171°. Yield 1 g. (Found: C, 73.48; H, 6.46. $C_{15}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 73.77; H, 6.55%).

2,6,7,9-Tetramethyl-5-oxo-5H-2,3-dihydrofuro(3,2-g)benzopyran (IIb): 7-Hydroxy-6-allyl-2,3,8-trimethylchromone (1 g.) was triturated with con. sulphuric acid (10 ml.) on a water bath for 10 mins. Working up as above, the compound crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 204°. Yield 0.6 g. (Found: C, 73.50; H, 6.26. $C_{15}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 73.77; H, 6.55%).

2,6,7,9-Tetramethyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran (IIIc): A mixture of 2,6,7,9-tetramethyl-5-oxo-5H-2,3-dihydrofuro(3,2-g)benzopyran (0.5 g.), palladised charcoal (10%; 0.3 g.) and diphenyl ether (4 ml.) was refluxed for 6 hr. Working up as above, the product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 237°. Yield 0.2 g. (Found: C, 74.04; H, 5.50. $C_{15}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 74.35; H, 5.78%).

7-Hydroxy-8-methylflavone (Ih): A mixture of 2-methyl resorcinol (5 g.), ethyl benzoyl-acetate (5 ml.) and diphenyl ether (10 ml.) was refluxed for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and the separated product was filtered. It was washed several times with petroleum ether and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 254°. Yield 1.5 g. (Found: C, 76.04; H, 4.68. $C_{18}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 76.16; H, 4.76%).

7-Allyloxy-8-methylflavone (Ii): A mixture of 7-hydroxy-8-methylflavone (2 g.), allyl bromide (1.8 ml.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (8 g.) and acetone (150 ml.) was refluxed on a water bath for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as before and the product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 163°. Yield 1.3 g. (Found: C, 78.14; H, 5.39. $C_{19}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 78.08; H, 5.49%).

7-Hydroxy-6-allyl-8-methylflavone (If): 7-Allyloxy-8-methylflavone (2 g.) was refluxed with dimethyl aniline (10 ml.) for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was poured into con. hydrochloric acid (30 ml.) containing pieces of ice. The separated product was filtered and dissolved in dilute sodium hydroxide solution. The solution was filtered and the filtrate on acidification with con. hydrochloric acid afforded the pure product. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 242°. Yield 1.4 g. (Found: C, 78.09; H, 5.39. $C_{19}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 78.08; H, 5.49%).

2,9-Dimethyl-7-phenyl-5-oxo-5H-2,3-dihydrofuro(3,2-g)benzopyran (IIc): 7-Hydroxy-6-allyl-8-methylflavone (1 g.) was triturated with conc. sulphuric acid (5 ml.) on a water bath for 15 mins. Working up as described earlier; the compound crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 220°. Yield 0.6 g. (Found: C, 78.07; H, 5.53. $C_{19}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 78.08; H, 5.49%).

2,9-Dimethyl-7-phenyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran (IIIId): A mixture of 2,9-dimethyl-7-phenyl-5-oxo-5H-2,3-dihydrofuro(3,2-g) benzopyran (0.5 g.) and palladised charcoal (10%; 0.3 g.) was refluxed with diphenyl ether (4 ml.) for 6 hr. Working up as described earlier, the product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 205°. Yield 0.2 g. (Found: C, 78.39; H, 4.59. $C_{19}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 78.61; H, 4.82%).

7-Hydroxy-6-acetaldehydo-8-methylflavone (Ik): 7-Hydroxy-6-allyl-8-methylflavone (1 g.) was dissolved in ethyl acetate (50 ml.). The solution was cooled to 0° by keeping it in freezing mixture. Ozonized oxygen was passed through it for 30 mins. It was hydrogenated in an atmosphere of hydrogen in the presence of palladised charcoal (5%; 0.5 g.) for 2 hr. The solution was filtered and the solvent was evaporated. The residue was dissolved in benzene and the solution was run over a short column of alumina. The product was eluted with benzene. Benzene was evaporated and the residue crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 238°. Yield 0.6 g. (Found: C, 73.51; H, 4.68. $C_{18}H_{13}O_4$ requires C, 73.72; H, 4.44%).

9-Methyl-7-phenyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran (IIIe): 7-Hydroxy-6-acetaldehydo-8-methylflavone (0.5 g.) was heated with *o*-phosphoric acid (8 ml.) on a water bath for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice. The separated product was filtered, washed with very dilute sodium hydroxide solution to remove uncyclised compound and it crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 220°. Yield 0.25 g. (Found: C, 78.27; H, 4.59. $C_{18}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 78.27; H, 4.35%).

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